

Online Product Review System: A tool to capture customer's perspective in Oman

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Abstract:

In the rapid growth of technology in this world, Oman is not an exception to buy mobile and laptop products depends on trend. With the popularization of different models, the consumers need to consider carefully the technical specifications, price, quality and other related information to improve the shopping experience. The online product review is the tool can be used to increase the value of the product. This article will review the mac and android products. The research work will bring out the analysis results of the best products preferred by the consumers of Oman. Also this study brings the characteristics of the most important products which may bring higher impact in the sales.